

AI Driven Strategies for Distributed Caching – A Case Study Using CMS Cache Data

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Motivation

- High Energy Physics (HEP) experiments like CMS at CERN **generate petabytes of data**, distributed globally for analysis
- Ensuring data locality is crucial to avoid redundant data transfers, reduce latency, and improve resource utilization in distributed computing environments
- **Traditional caching policies (LRU, LFU)** use static heuristics and struggle with evolving access patterns in HEP workloads
- With **exponentially increasing data volumes in the next decade**, there is an urgent need for adaptive and intelligent caching strategies to maintain performance

Background

- High Energy Physics (HEP) is a field of science dedicated to understand the fundamental particles and forces that constitute the universe.
- These large-scale research facilities are typically operated by international collaborations like CERN in Europe, Fermilab in the U.S. and KEK in Japan leading the efforts.
- The Large Hadron Collider (LHC), the world's largest and most powerful particle accelerator, led to the discovery of the Higgs Boson in 2012.

Background

- The Open Science Grid (OSG) is a distributed computing infrastructure designed to support large-scale scientific research across various disciplines
- The Open Science Data Federation (OSDF) is a component of the OSG ecosystem designed to manage and distribute large-scale scientific data.
- OSG provides a user-friendly interface for geographically distributed researchers to access its computation and storage resource

Introduction

- Implemented a **deep learning-based caching strategy** using a **Deep Recurrent Neural Network (DRNN)** model (LSTM + GRU)
- **Predict upcoming file accesses** to prefetch and retain them in cache, enhancing data locality.
- Conducted **comparative analysis** against traditional LRU and LFU in a simulated **Open Science Pool (OSPool)** environment
- Demonstrated **improvements in cache hit rates, reduced network latency, and optimized bandwidth utilization** with minimal computational overhead

Methodology

- Data Collection
- Model Design
- Experiment Setup
- Deployment

Methodology – Data Collection

Data Source

Collected from Real-time CMS cache logs from **SoCal MINI site (UCSD)**

Data structure

Comprises of **62 attributes** and **372,586 records** over 1 month period.

Key attributes

file name, file size, server site, server domain, timestamp, user, read bytes...

Access Frequency

Daily file accesses per cache ranged between **~2,900 to ~74,000** (including maintenance).

Methodology – Model Design

- Aggregated accesses into **hourly intervals**, tracking **top-3 file accesses** per hour to model popularity trends.
- Developed a **Deep Recurrent Neural Network (DRNN)** using **LSTM + GRU layers**.
- Trained to **predict top-3 file accesses for the next hour**, enabling prefetching.
- Model trained on **high-activity days** to capture diverse patterns and improve generalization.

Methodology – Experimental Setup

- Cache node is **simulated**, data was fed into cache along with their file sizes
- Used **actual cache sizes, link speeds, file sizes** from the dataset
- In **Case-3**, predicted files are either:
 - Retained if already present
 - Prefetched if absent

Scenario	Prefetching	Eviction
Case-1	No	LRU
Case-2	No	LFU
Case-3	DRNN-based	LFU

Methodology – Experimental Setup

- Introduced **pinning strategy** to retain predicted files in cache for one hour to avoid premature eviction
- Ran simulation over continuous time windows to **mimic live cache operation.**
- Deployed workloads using **HTCondor on OSPool** to test scalability and throughput.
- Measured key metrics: **hit rate, miss rate, network latency, and bandwidth utilization** under all scenarios

Methodology – Deployment (OSPool)

- Utilized OSPool's High-Throughput Computing (HTC) infrastructure via **HTCondor** for large-scale distributed execution.
- Packaged dependencies (TensorFlow, Scikit-learn) **using Apptainer** for a reproducible environment.
- Despite queue times, the model made predictions **in under 30 seconds**, showing **minimal overhead and suitability** for real-world deployment.

Results & Discussion

Hit rates for different cache nodes following LRU, LFU, and Prefetching + LFU eviction strategies

Overview of pinned hits and their contribution in the overall cache hits for different cache nodes

Results & Discussion

Network Latencies for different cache nodes with LRU, LFU, and Prefetching + LFU strategies

Cache Node	N/w Latency improvement (vs LRU)	N/w Latency improvement (vs LFU)
Cache-1	-18.0 sec	-6.0 sec
Cache-2	-22.8 sec	0.0 sec
Cache-3	-10.2 sec	-6.0 sec
Cache-4	-42.6 sec	-20.4 sec

Network Latencies for different cache nodes with LRU, LFU, and Prefetching + LFU strategies

Results & Discussion

Cache node	Pinned Storage	Pinned Hits	Next Hour requests	Total Requests	Cache Hit Rate	Pinned Hit Rate
Cache-1	55.53%	124	424	5907	41.27%	29.25%
Cache-2	26.65%	50	399	6389	47.87%	12.53%
Cache-3	26.71%	86	541	6132	51.20%	15.89%
Cache-4	53.76%	147	701	10550	38.80%	20.97%

Overview of pinned data accesses contribution in the hit rates

Conclusion

- The paper presents how an **AI-driven predictive caching strategy** developed using a Deep Recurrent Neural Network (DRNN) with LSTM + GRU layers
- Integrated the model into a **realistic cache simulation** and compared against traditional **LRU and LFU** policies
- The **Prefetching + LFU** approach showed **improved cache hit rates, reduced network latency, optimized bandwidth usage**
- Introduced a **pinning mechanism** to retain predicted files and maximize cache usefulness.
- Deployed and tested the strategy on **OSPool**, demonstrating **low computational overhead and feasibility in production environments.**

Future Work

- Enhance responsiveness to **dynamic and evolving access patterns** in distributed systems.
- Integrate **reinforcement learning** to dynamically decide when and what to prefetch or evict.
- Develop **adaptive pinning strategies** that balance hit rate and cache space more effectively
- Evaluate performance on **larger-scale multi-site cache networks**

Thank You

Questions?